

ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation: *The educator can effectively use various exhibitions, technical means to make the educational process more effective. Great of our thinkers unique works, their wise words, different heroism plates described pictures, manners on the subject movies technician tools as upbringing " effect does .*

The key word : *upbringing, eyes, creative work, wise word*

Human spiritual competent so in upbringing uzbek of the people national and cultural values use , source studies teaching to the goal is compatible . Educational measures in planning student psyche , curiosity in the process positive and negative qualities availability level attention give , educate measures quality and efficiency in increasing new performance methods and forms use to the art has to be pedagogical pedagogical mastery depending on . Of educators this difficult cocktails appreciated in case students themselves raw close assistant be need _ That's it in place Voiz Kashifi 's "If you are a disciple binosi of what on top if they ask that it be built answer bergil : Will and sabr patience , what teacher istasa , uni jon ear with sincere to hear with acceptance to make believable is to be ." words is appropriate .

Students cocktail state by suitable in a way appreciation their ability more develops their _ creative activity improve , own on take growing works improves , to himself given to the award positive answer gives _ Of course this in place xar a educator pedagogical organization skill has to be need _ Education process right organization , of course then students empty time distribution need _ Bunda students parents with closely attitude be they need _ with conversations following directions take to go must :

1. The student character feature , family place , position , psyche condition in the study .
2. Odob and morality doir conversation _ (east customs , rituals , new _ came out publications) .

3. Education complicated students to his parents advice give ,

When a teacher's one-on-one conversations are thorough, well-founded, and logically rich, they increase a parent's confidence in him or her - resulting in a state of cooperation, such as free speech, advice, and mutual assistance.

Teacher one-on-one and students with one-on-one activities set off put for parents identity , family condition to know need _ Teacher parents about information has since then their children about information identify get is important . Pedagoguing students complete learning , educational measures perfect impressive to organize opportunity creates _

Teacher own activities to the following attention give must :

1. In students formed coming positive qualities describe them _ knowledge to take curiosity , honesty , enlightenment , kindness , friendship , self management ,

mehnatg a attitude development _

2. Students mental power and temperament types separate get _

3. In the student positive and salbii change observation and cause learn _

4. In the student lie to speak and other negative qualities detection _

Students with different travels organization , cinemas go , games

It is advisable to organize, hold nights dedicated to the holidays.

For example : " Flowers holiday " morning transfer students aesthetic xis feelings

grows . Holidays transfer the goal in students year seasons seasonal to observe changes, to give insights into the flora of nature, the various flowers, their growth, and so on.

Science educators xar kind of competitions competitions transfer raw adds knowledge to the student's knowledge, develops his / her worldview, strengthens communication with his / her peers; encourages independent thinking. Various clubs organized in colleges also had a positive effect on the education of students. Whichever educator is an organizer, eager for innovation, his students grow up to be friendly and kind. They are of friends , parents , educators , of science appreciate enough competent man become growing grow .

Of our state eng great purpose raw original that is .

Of these lines xar one on clear think exemplary , scientific jixatdan based on affairs plan , pedagogues team his educational works

level come outgoing system to be necessary .

Education _ in the process student to know old interests a lot sided in appearance show will be : student mobile and curiosity , to some of the student's academic activities as well as to reading in general motives , student identity to himself specific signs and his direction decision find

mother these are including .

Student young period specific natural activity , a a mental interest with cover if not , it which side from go away in advance to say difficult _ Therefore for also KDUshinsky " rape and to force based on teaching " student had emphasized that hych had no effect on mental development. It should be noted that the interests and motives students study

depending on the degree of formation of their activities is manifested in a complex relationship with the initial factors that shape the personality (the student's theoretical opinion, the importance of learning activities for the student's personality).

Lesson in the process students knowledge activities management a how much

factors depending on . Their eng from the basics one students own faniga curious is to take . Scientists as noted , only curious psychic processes and their perception , attention , memory , contemplation and iroda such as functions positive effect shows .

Well , students to read (to know) interests formation

terms how _ Mohir teacher them in the classroom in students formation , training activities activation and to read which was interests always developing to go for what to do do you need

A skilled teacher shapes students 'interest in reading and always developing to go for to the following amal do important :

1. Students to knowledge aspiration , science in general when mental to labor interests development training process so formed mature provides that _ student active movement makes , independent research and new factors

" discover || to reach , problematic situations itself hal to reach strives .

2. Training activity other activities such as only different only when interesting will be . One kind of method information give and a kind of method actions fast there boredom to the body brings _

3. Fanga which was curiosity in shaping this fanni and his some parts study necessity , importance and to the goal compatibility to students mean very much is necessary .

4. The material being taught with previous material How more bind explained to those students so much more interesting it seems . Training material

students curious things with bind explain them too to the lesson of interest important role plays .

5. Average in difficulty training materials in students interest does not wake up .

Training materials a oz harder , but students power enough to be need _

6. Students performed work often check also their fanga which was arouses interest.

7. Accuracy of teaching material, richness of emotion, enjoyment of the teacher

to speak student fanga which was curiosity increase very much big effect shows .

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